

Characteristics of Consumer with Product Satisfaction in Jakarta "Desa Spa" Company

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine consumer characteristics, consumer satisfaction with spa products/services, and the relationship between consumer characteristics and customer satisfaction. The characteristics of the consumers studied were: gender, age, last education level, occupation, visit to-, source of information, willingness to come back, appropriateness of price, and ease of location. The unit of analysis in this study is the individual, namely the consumers at the Spa. The data analysis methods used are: (1) descriptive statistics, which describe the frequency distribution and percentage of respondents' answers, and (2) Chi Square statistics, which are statistics to test independence. The

conclusion obtained shows that most of the Spa consumers are: women, Indonesian citizens, aged between 20 – 40 years, have a Diploma/S1 education, work employees / students, get information from brochures/ friends / internet, willing to come back, think the price is right, consider the location already good, and put the product/service as the most important. The relationship between consumer characteristics and Spa services shows that nationality, education, occupation, sources of information and location do not have a significant relationship with a service. Meanwhile, gender, age, frequency of visits, pricing and service availability are significantly related to satisfaction

Keywords:- Satisfaction, Spa.

I. INTRODUCTION

PT. Indo Desa Spa, which operates a chain of day spas, in Jakarta, Bali, Kuala Lumpur, and Malaysia's Penang Island, has its own buildings and also opens in hotels. Desa Spa is headquartered on Jl. Wolter Monginsidi No. 25, Kebayoran Baru, Jakarta. In addition, Desa Spa also provides spa products as well as therapist education.

As one of the mainstay sectors, tourism is expected to encourage an increase in the country's foreign exchange through the flow of tourist arrivals from abroad who spend their income in Indonesia. The trend that is currently developing is tourist attractions/attractions related to tourism health. It is believed that activities carried out by tourists related to health problems such as Spa, which is one of the tourism products with great potential, which fulfills health rules will get added value from the tourists who always use it, so that the product is guaranteed quality from its users.

Spa is one of the tourism products that is currently growing rapidly in Indonesia and has its own charm and uniqueness that is different from spas in other countries, because of that, spas in Indonesia have advantages and are very competitive in international forums. In fact, nowadays many hotels and travel agencies make spa packages. Spas can now be found everywhere, complete with various treatment programs. Some offer multi-day treatment packages and some are practical short programs.

Regarding its development, spa is closely related to bathing (showering), and of course with the material used, namely water. Since ancient times, water is a very vital element for the existence and development of human civilization. All growth in this world, is very dependent on the presence of water. From time to time, humans have used water as an extraordinary power to prevent various diseases and become a means of health or what is known as hydrotherapy. In the 20th century, the existence of spas began to change slightly in orientation, no longer as healing, but as a means of preventing and maintaining health and wellness.

At this time, the spa becomes a health center and a place to cultivate the health of the mind, body, and spiritual. People go to the spa because they want to release all the tension of the mind, calm the mind, relax, healthy lifestyle, and fit. The spa, which combines traditional and modern techniques, Eastern and Western styles, has so far satisfied many customers from all walks of life. Today, spa is the ideal place to get a complete feeling of wellness, and a suitable place to get natural health therapy. Some people think of SPA as an abbreviation of Healthy Using Air or Tirta Husada. In Article 7.d. of the Tourism Law, spas are included as one or part of the recreational and entertainment business group.

There are many urgent aspects that must be understood by spa management, including: how is the competition map in the spa business, who are the competitors, what are the strengths and weaknesses of the competitors, accuracy in segmenting consumers, whether the current marketing mix

can be achieved. Reach the target market segment, and of course, whether consumers are satisfied with the product/service and so on. For this reason, this study focuses on the discussion on how the characteristics of tourists affect the level of satisfaction in using spa products.

Based on the description above, it can be stated that customer satisfaction is the most significant thing in Spa services. For this reason, knowledge about segmentation is an additional thing that must be considered. For this reason, the problems raised in this study include three main things as follows:

- Not yet known consumer satisfaction with Spa products.
- The segmentation of the Spa consumer market is not yet known.
- Not yet known the factors of consumer characteristics related to consumer satisfaction with Spa products.

Referring to the description above, there are three formulations of the problems developed as follows:

- How is customer satisfaction with Spa products?
- How is the segmentation of the Spa consumer market?
- Are consumer characteristics related to customer satisfaction with Spa products?

In accordance with the identification and formulation of the problem above, the objectives of this study can be described as follows:

- Knowing the level of customer satisfaction with the service packages at the Spa.
- Knowing the Spa consumer market segmentation.
- Knowing whether the characteristics (nationality, gender, age, education, and occupation) are relate to consumer satisfaction with Spa products.

II. THEORY BASIC

A. Definition of Spa

Regarding its development, spa is closely related to bathing (showering), and of course with the material used, namely water. Since ancient times, water is a very vital element for the existence and development of human civilization. All growth in this world, is very dependent on the presence of water. From time to time, humans have used water as an extraordinary power to prevent various diseases and become a means of health or what is called hydrotherapy, derived from the Greek words Hydor (water) and Therapeia (healing). (Travel Club Magazine, Spa, Between Fitness, Lifestyle, and Recreation, January, 2004 edition). Aqua or Solus Par Aqua which means treatment using water media.

B. *Travel Club Magazine, January 2004 issue, stated that:*

- *In Greek, spa is an abbreviation of Sante Par Aqua, While in Latin, spa is an abbreviation of Sanus Per Aquam or Salute Per Aqua, which is defined as a way to gain health through water therapy (aqua therapy), or relaxation through water.*
- *The word spa itself comes from the Latin, Espa (spring), and Sparsa from Spargere (splash or splash)*

In Indonesia, some people think of SPA as an abbreviation of Healthy Using Air or Tirta Husada. The

definition of SPA according to the Indonesian Ministry of Health, which is sufficient to summarize, is as follows:

“SPA is a traditional health effort that uses a holistic approach, through comprehensive treatments using a combination method of hydrotherapy, massage, and other skills, which are held in an integrated manner to balance the body, mind, and feelings (body, mind, and spirit)”

“ Water therapy (hydrotherapy) is the use of water and/or with natural ingredients (plants, minerals, essential oils, salt, milk, mud, body scrubs) for body health care, by regulating temperature, pressure, current, humidity, and water content.”

“Massage is a body care technique by means of massage that uses movements of the limbs (hands, fingers, elbows, feet) and/or other aids on soft tissues (skin, muscles, and nerves) which gives a stimulating, relaxing, smoothing effect. Circulation of blood, circulation of lymph (lymphatic)

“ Aromatherapy (aromatherapy) is a body care technique using/utilizing essential oils which are efficacious: it can be inhaled, compressed, applied to the skin, soaked, and will be more effective accompanied by massage. The ingredients used are active substances taken from the essence of aromatic plants (extracted from flowers, leaves, roots, stems/twigs, fruits, seeds, etc.) which provide a stimulating or relaxing effect.

“ Relaxation is an effort to reduce fatigue, tension, boredom, both physically and mentally.

“Rejuvenation is an effort to rejuvenate the body to realize the beauty of appearance”

“Revitalization is an effort to empower healthy organ functions so that a more optimal level of health is obtained”

Various SPA techniques: can be divided based on the character, as follows:

- **Spa, Salon, Day Spa, or City Spa.** Spas do not provide accommodation and are usually located within the city to provide one-day body treatments.
- **Resort Spas.** Spas, which are located in the middle of nature, usually provide accommodation and are used for visitors who want to relax for a few days.
- **Destination Spa,** a Spa that provides treatments and therapies for the patient's specific goals. For example, there are people who want to shrink their stomach or lose weight.
- **Cruise Spas.** Spas on cruise ships
- **Medical Spa.** A spa in collaboration with a hospital. Usually, this spa provides therapies for people who have had surgery or accidents. Usually, the equipment for medical spas will be more modern than other types of spas.
- **Club Spa.** A special spa for its members only.

The keen tourism and hospitality industry, especially hotels, are developing their fantastic imaginations about spas, creating new types and colors of their own, such as:

- **Chinese Herbal Bath.** Spa, with therapeutic massage techniques, body scrub with fresh watermelon, and face with

golden yellow jackfruit accompanied by reflexology, manicure, and pedicure.

- **Traditional Medicine.** Spa for executives, pregnant women, disabled people, including babies who can just crawl, with Chinese, Japanese, Thai systems, using steam bath, sauna, jacuzzi, and swimming pool facilities.
- **Ayurvedic treatment.** Spa, with massage and rubbing techniques with henna (henna) ingredients, milk, turmeric, oil, fresh herbs, and powder for physical and spiritual balance, and restore identity.
- **Stay young.** Spa, in particular, for those who already feel old by massaging, massaging the fat under the surface of the skin in a holistic therapy and naturopathy (fresh plant ingredients).
- **Physical and Spiritual Harmony.** A full body spa, for 1 hour, with a concoction of seaweed and oil-producing herbs from distant mountains, which is hard to remember. Meanwhile, the cranium is massaged with the nose, ears and neck being cleaned therapeutically with warm stones. When finished, it is recommended that you sleep with your body on your back straight without a pillow.
- **Fresh Fit Always.** These include a Javanese scrub, bath, a Singapore-style various flower ritual in a bath, and a Thai massage.

Based on the type of service, according to the Indonesian Ministry of Health, spas can be categorized into three groups:

- The minimal category includes spa treatments using simple hydrotherapy, relaxing massage, and/or simple aromatherapy and self-appearance manually and/or with simple equipment.
- The medium category includes spa treatments using hydrotherapy with medium equipment, relaxing massage with moderate equipment, and/or with moderate aromatherapy, and beauty of self-appearance with medium equipment.
- The main categories include spa treatments using hydrotherapy complex equipment, relaxing massage complex equipment, and/or complex aromatherapy and beauty self-appearance complex equipment.

Despite the above criteria, not all spas are covered by these criteria. Spas come in all shapes, sizes and foci.

C. Understanding Consumer Satisfaction

According to Purnomo Edwin Setyo (2017), explaining that consumer satisfaction is;

"Is one of the important elements in improving marketing performance in a company". The Satisfaction felt by customers can increase the intensity of buying from these customers. With the creation of an optimal level of customer satisfaction, it encourages the creation of loyalty in the minds of satisfied customers. According to Kotler and Keller (2016) states that consumer satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises after comparing the expected product performance (results) to the expected performance (or results). If performance is below expectations, consumers are dissatisfied. If performance exceeds expectations, consumers are very satisfied / happy. From the two opinions above, it is clear that customer satisfaction is something that determines the company's success.

According to Fandy Tjiptono (2014: p.353) Satisfaction comes from the Latin, namely states which means enough (enough), and

face which means to do (to do). So, in simple terms, it can be interpreted as an effort to fulfill something. So, a product or service that can satisfy is a product or service that is able to provide something that consumers are looking for to a sufficient level. In the context of consumer behavior theory, they get good service or satisfaction is more defined from the perspective of consumer experience after consuming or using a product or service.

D. Consumer Satisfaction Criteria

The level of customer satisfaction with services is an important factor in developing a service delivery system that is responsive to consumer needs, minimizing costs and time and maximizing the impact of services to the target population.

According to Zeithaml and Bitner (in Firmansyah, 2018) the factors that influence consumer satisfaction is as follows:

- Product quality, is a key influence because consumers are satisfied when the product used quality
- Quality of service or services, namely consumers will feel satisfied if it is in accordance with what expected.
- Emotion that consumers will feel proud and gain confidence that people others will be amazed at him if he uses a product with a certain brand that has a higher level of satisfaction. The satisfaction obtained is not because of the quality of the product but social or self-esteem that makes consumers feel satisfied with a certain brand
- Price is a product that has high quality the same but set a relative price cheap will give more value high to consumers.
- Costs are unnecessary consumers incur additional costs or not, need to waste time to get a product or service tends to be satisfied to the product or service.

➤ Consumer Satisfaction Benefits

According to Tjiptono and Chandra (2012;57), customer satisfaction has two main benefits for the company, namely in the form of customer loyalty and word of mouth advertising or what is commonly called positive word of mouth. .

E. Measuring and Evaluating Consumers

According to Kotler quoted from the book Service, Quality and Satisfaction by Fandy Tjiptono (2014: 219) there are four methods of measuring consumer satisfaction, namely:

➤ Complaint and Suggestion Systems

Every consumer-oriented company needs to provide the widest possible opportunity for consumers to submit their suggestions, opinions, and complaints. Media that can be used include suggestion boxes placed in strategic places, for example by providing comment cards and special telephone lines (customer hotlines).

➤ Customer Satisfaction Surveys

In general, research on consumer satisfaction is conducted using a survey method (Tjiptono, 2000). Through surveys, the company will get responses and feedback from consumers as well as give a positive sign that the company pays attention to its consumers.

➤ *Ghost Shopping*

This method is implemented by employing several people (ghost shoppers) to act and act as potential consumers/buyers of the company's or competitor's products. Then the ghost shopper conveys his findings regarding the strengths and weaknesses of the company's or competitors' products based on their experience in buying these products. In addition, ghosting shoppers can also observe or assess the way the company and its competitors respond to consumer questions and respond to any complaints.

➤ *Lost Customer Analysis*

This method is quite unique. The company tries to contact consumers who have stopped buying or who have switched manufacturers. With this method, it is hoped that information on the causes of this occurrence will be obtained. This information is very useful for companies to obtain further policies in order to increase customer satisfaction and loyalty.

In evaluating consumer satisfaction with a particular product, service or company, consumers generally refer to various factors or dimensions. Factors that are often used in evaluating satisfaction with a product, according to Hawkins and Lonney quoted in Tjiptono (2010):

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➤ *Conformance of Expectations*

is a level the match between the expected product performance right by the customer with what is felt by customers, including:

- The product obtained matches or exceeds expectations.
- The services provided by employees match or exceed what is expected.
- Supporting facilities obtained are in accordance with or exceeding what is expected.

➤ *Interest to visit again*

It is the customer's willingness to visit again or do Repurchase of related products,

- Interested to visit again because the service provided by employees is satisfactory
- Interested to visit again because of the value and benefits that obtained after consuming the product.
- Interested to visit again because of the supporting facilities provided adequate

➤ *Willingness to Recommend*

It is a customer's willingness to recommend a product that he has tasted to friends or family, including:

- It is a customer's willingness to recommend a product that he has tasted to friends or family, including:
- Advise friends or relatives to buy the products offered because the supporting facilities provided are adequate.
- Advise friends or relatives to buy the products offered because of the value or benefits obtained after consuming a product or service.

F. *Consumer Segmentation*

Markets are made up of buyers, and buyers differ in one way or another. They can have different desires, resources they have, places, buying attitudes, and buying practices that they do. Through market segmentation, companies dividing a large and heterogeneous market into small segments, so that it can be reached by the company more efficiently and effectively, with products and services that suit the needs of consumers in that segment.

According to Ridwansyah (2017:16) the elements of a marketing strategy can be classified into three main elements, namely:

- Market segmentation is a process of dividing market into segments (groups) that smaller based on certain characteristics
- Targeting is the process of determining the segment customers to be served (and not serve) by company
- Positioning is a process of showing certain image of the company in mind targeted customers.

According to Philip Kotler & Kevin (2009), market segmentation is an effort to improve the company's marketing accuracy. In order to be of maximum benefit, market segments must meet the following five characteristics:

➤ *Can be measured (Measurable)*

The size, purchasing power and profile of the segment must be measurable. Certain segmentation variables are difficult to measure

➤ *Large (Substantial)*

The segment must be large and profitable enough to serve. A segment must be the largest possible homogeneous group value sought by the marketing program tailor-made for them.

➤ *Can be reached (accessible)*

Segments can be reached and served effectively. For example, a perfume company found that heavy users of its brand were single women who worked late into the night and frequented bars. If these women do not live or shop in certain places and are not highlighted by certain media, then they will be difficult to reach.

➤ *Differentiable (Differentiable)*

Segments can be separated conceptually and respond differently to different elements and programs of the marketing mix. If married and unmarried women give the same response in purchasing cosmetics, then they are not a different segment.

➤ *Actionable*

Effective programs can be formulated to attract and serve the relevant segments. For example, an airline company identifies eight market segments, so as a consequence, the company must be able to provide adequate resources to be able to develop separate marketing programs for each of these segments.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a case study conducted in a spa company in Jakarta. The unit of analysis in this study is the individual, namely the consumer. The consumers in this study are male/female individuals who have enjoyed servicing at the Spa. In general, the measured variables are divided into 2 types, namely demographic variables and satisfaction variables.

The data used in this study include primary data and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained directly from data sources, while secondary data is data obtained from indirect sources related to the research topic (Kuncoro, 2003)

Sampling of respondents was carried out using purposive sampling or professional judgment. Determination of the number of samples was carried out by The Slovin method after the size of the population was known.

To answer the first and second problems, namely how satisfaction with Spa products and consumer segmentation, descriptive statistics are used, which describe the frequency distribution and percentage of respondents' answers. Chi Square stats. Chi Square is a statistic to test for independence. Chi Square is used to test whether two variables are not related. In this study, the variables to be tested are consumer characteristics with consumer satisfaction with the product. The Chi Square equation is as follows:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{j=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(A_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}}$$

- Where :
- χ^2 = Chi Square count
- A_{ij} = Frequency actually in row 1
column j
- E_{ij} = Frequency expectations in row
I, column j, if the two variables
are independent
- r = Number of Lines
- c = Number of Column

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ Consumer Characteristics

The following will discuss the characteristics of consumers obtained from data collection through questionnaires.

➤ Citizenship

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, all of the respondents answered questions about citizenship, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

From the Consumer Distribution table based on nationality, it is known that Indonesian citizens are 92.4%,

Chinese and British citizens are 2.2%, Dutch, Irish, Japanese citizens are 1.1%

➤ Gender

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, all of the respondents answered questions about gender, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

From the Consumer Distribution Table by Gender, it is known that there are more female consumers (60.9%) than male consumers (39.1%). This happens, allegedly, because women are synonymous with beauty, beauty, and tidiness. One alternative to maintain that image, is to try to spend more time and budget to visit the existing spa.

➤ Consumer Age

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, three people did not give an answer, 89 people answered the question about age, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

➤ From the Consumer Distribution Table by age,

It is known that the most consumers are aged 20 – 30 years (56.2%), followed by the age of 31 – 40 years (27%), less than 20 years (10.1%), the next age is 41 – 50 years (5.6%), and the last one was 51-60 years old. This happens, allegedly, because the age of 20 – 30 years is a productive young age, where they have their own income, are not yet married, have a need to try something new, look attractive, and enjoy life. Of course, visiting the spa is one alternative that is appropriate and rational for them.

➤ Consumer's Last Education

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, eight people did not give an answer, 84 people answered the question about the last education, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

From the Consumer Distribution Table by Education, it is known that most consumers have Diploma/S1 education (73.8%), followed by Masters (15.5%), up to high school (equivalent) (9.5%), and the last is education S3 (1.2%). This happens, presumably, because people with Diploma/S1 education are more educated than high school graduates, but do not yet have as many needs as graduates of S2 or S3. Thus, they have more extra money to meet secondary needs.

➤ Consumer Jobs

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, all of them answered questions about their work, and the following distribution was obtained:

From the Consumer Distribution Table by occupation, it is known that most consumer consumers are employees (33.7%) and students (27.2%), while the next order is housewives (7.6%), civil servants (3.3%), teachers and retirees 1.1% each. This happens, presumably, because employees in Jakarta experience relatively high work pressure, so they need more atmosphere, time, and place for relaxation to relieve the daily fatigue and boredom they experience at work. And spas are certainly a good alternative

for them. In addition, employees have more income than other jobs such as teachers, housewives, retirees, and civil servants. Meanwhile, college students, who are mostly young, tend to look more attractive/beautiful, and tend to try new things with their friends.

➤ *Arrival Frequency*

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, 1 person was not willing to give an answer, and 91 people gave an answer about the number of visits to the Spa until the time of the study, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

From the Consumer Distribution Table based on Visits, it is known that the least consumers are those who visit 4 times (4.4%) to 5 times (3.3%), while in the first visit (19.8%), the 2nd time (17.6%), 3 times (26.4%), and more than five times (28.6%) were relatively high. This, allegedly, because on the first visit consumers want to try the services available at the Spa. Satisfied they tried a second time. On their third arrival, they reached a saturation level, and tried other spa alternatives. Thus, the fourth and fifth visits to the Spa have greatly decreased. After trying in other places and comparing with the services at the Spa, consumers feel more comfortable at the Spa, so they decide to become regular customers in the future.

➤ *Resources*

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, all of them gave answers about the sources of information about Spa up to the time of the study, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

The Table of Consumer Distribution based on Sources of Information about Spas above shows that most consumers get information from brochures (32.6%), while friends (19.6%), magazines (16.3%) and the internet (15.2%) occupy second place, and the last is family advice (4.3%) and board (3.3%). This, presumably, was because the brochure was simpler, in which the product, address, and price were clearly stated. So, with the information from the brochure, consumers feel they are ready with everything, including the costs to be paid.

➤ *Willingness to Come Back*

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, 1 person was not willing to give an answer, 91 people gave an answer about their willingness to come back to the Spa until the time of the study, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

From the Consumer Distribution Table based on willingness to come back, it is known that most consumers are willing to come back (82.4%), while 17.6% are not. High willingness of consumers to come This return, allegedly, because consumers are pampered with the services of a satisfactory therapist, adequate treatment facilities, and attractive and attractive interior design.

This return, allegedly, because consumers are pampered with the services of a satisfactory therapist, adequate treatment facilities, and an attractive interior design and

provide a comfortable atmosphere. This makes the Spa can be a place of body, mind, and soul recovery for consumers.

➤ *Compatibility between the price offered by the spa and the services/products provided*

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, 1 person was not willing to give an answer, 91 people gave an answer about the suitability of the price of Spa services to the time of the study, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

From the Distribution Table of Consumers based on Price - Service Suitability, it is known that most consumers think that the price is in accordance with what is received (82.4%), while 17.6% do not agree. This, allegedly, is because professional Spa therapists are able to provide gentle massage touches, good and correct communication, which are packaged together with the comfort of the room atmosphere, which is not found in other spas. The shady atmosphere is able to reduce consumer price sensitivity.

➤ *Convenient Location*

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, 1 person was not willing to give an answer, 91 people gave an answer about the ease of reaching the Spa location, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

From the Consumer Distribution Table based on the ease of reaching the Spa location, it is known that the most consumers answered that it was easy to reach the Spa location (85.7%), while the remaining (14.3%) answered that it was not easy to reach. This is presumably due to the Spa's location on the main road, strategic, easy to reach, accessible, good access, and traversed by many vehicles.

➤ *Consumer Satisfaction with Spa in general*

Of the 92 people who responded to the questionnaire, 2 people were not willing to give an answer, 90 people gave an answer about satisfaction with the Spa in general, and the distribution was obtained as follows:

From the Table of Consumer Satisfaction with Spa, it is generally known that most consumers answered satisfied (80.0%), those who answered very satisfied (13.3%), and those who answered average (6.7%). So, in general, consumers are quite satisfied with the Spa.

➤ *Relationship between Consumer Characteristics and Consumer Satisfaction at Spa*

• *Relationship between Citizenship and satisfaction with Consumer Satisfaction with Spa*

From the distribution of the questionnaires obtained and the Chi Square value between citizenship and consumer satisfaction in general with Spa is known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.999 is much greater than 5%, so it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship between citizenship and general consumer satisfaction with the Spa. This is, presumably, because Spas, in general, do set the same standard of service for all consumers who come to take services at the Spa.

- *The Relationship between Consumer Gender and Satisfaction with Spa*

From the distribution of the questionnaires obtained cross tabulation and the Chi Square value between sexes with general satisfaction with the Spa, it is known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.002 is much smaller than 5%, so it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between gender and general satisfaction with the Spa, where women more satisfied than men. With contingency coefficient = 0.355. It is suspected that because most of the management and implementers are women, the policies regarding programs and facilities at the Spa, consciously or not, lead to the fulfillment of feminine needs.

- *The relationship between age and satisfaction with Spa*

From the distribution of the questionnaires obtained cross tabulation and the Chi Square value between age and general customer satisfaction with the Spa, it is known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.007 is much smaller than 5%, so it is concluded that there is a significant relationship between age and general satisfaction with Spa, where young age more satisfied than the older. With a contingency coefficient = 0.440. This is, allegedly, because the concept of a spa is basically to refresh the body, relax the mind, and calm the soul. With great energy and enthusiasm, as well as with their great ability to absorb new things, with a little touch, young people are relatively easy to achieve these three things and come back refreshed. While old age is relatively inert to change, or shifts from one condition to the next, so it requires a longer and more understanding treatment.

- *The relationship between the last education of consumers with satisfaction with spa*

From the distribution of the questionnaires, it was obtained that the Chi Square value between the last education level and satisfaction with Spa was generally known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.157 was much greater than 5%, so it was concluded that there was no significant relationship between the last education level and satisfaction with Spa in general. This, it is suspected, is because the Spa management does not make programs or facilities that are differentiated based on the level of education or consumer perception.

- *The Relationship between Consumer Jobs and General Satisfaction with Spa*

From the distribution of questionnaires, it was obtained that the Chi Square value between work and satisfaction with the Spa was generally known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.055 was greater than 5%, so it was concluded that there was no significant relationship between work and satisfaction with the Spa in general. This, it is suspected, is because the Spa management does not make programs that are differentiated based on the work of consumers.

- *The Relationship between the Number of Consumer Visits with Satisfaction with Spa*

From the distribution of the questionnaires, cross tabulation was obtained and the Chi Square value between the

number of visits and satisfaction with the Spa was generally known that the Chi Square significance value was 0.044 less than 5%, so it was concluded that there was a significant relationship between the number of visits and satisfaction with the Spa in general. With a contingency coefficient = 0.417. This, allegedly, is because the reason consumers come to the spa is to refresh the body, relax the mind, and calm the soul. While the willingness to return is related to satisfaction with the Spa in general, as well as the price offered by the Spa, in general, according to most consumers, it is appropriate, the location is also easy to reach, while the Spa products themselves, in general, are rated as quite satisfactory. Thus, the three consumer needs have been met in a way that is cheap, easy, and quite satisfying.

- *The Relationship between Information Sources and General Satisfaction with Spa*

From the distribution of the questionnaires, it was obtained that the Chi Square value between the sources of information and satisfaction with the Spa was generally known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.912 was much greater than 5%, so it was concluded that there was no significant relationship between the sources of information and satisfaction with the Gaya Spa in general.

- *The Relationship between Consumer willingness to Come Back and General Satisfaction with Spa*

From the distribution of the questionnaires obtained cross tabulation and the Chi Square value between the willingness to come back and satisfaction with the Spa in general it is known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.000 is much smaller than 5%, so it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between the willingness to visit again and satisfaction with the Spa in general. where those who are willing to revisit tend to have higher satisfaction. With a contingency coefficient = 0.520.

- *Relationship between Fair Pricing and General Satisfaction with Spa*

From the distribution of the questionnaires obtained cross tabulation and the Chi Square value between reasonable pricing and satisfaction with the Spa in general, it is known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.000 is much smaller than 5%, so it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between price suitability with service and satisfaction with the Spa in general. In general, those who think the price is appropriate tend to be perceive the price is appropriate tend to have higher satisfaction. With a contingency coefficient = 0.566.

- *The relationship between the convenience of the location with general satisfaction with the spa*

From the questionnaire distribution, it was obtained that the Chi Square value between the convenience of the location and satisfaction with the Spa was generally known that the Chi Square significance value of 0.186 was much greater than 5%, so it was concluded that there was no significant relationship between the convenience of the location and satisfaction with the Spa in general.

• *Summary of Total Score Relationship Consumer Characteristics and Satisfaction with Spa*

From the results of the analysis of the collected questionnaire data, a summary of the contingency coefficients of the characteristics related to satisfaction is obtained as follows:

The most related to satisfaction with Spa in general is the suitability of price with service (0.566), the second is the willingness to come back (0.520), the third is age (0.440), the fourth is the visit (0.417), and the last is gender (0.355).

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

Some conclusions obtained from this research are as follows:

- Most of the Spa consumers are: Indonesian citizens, women, between the ages of 20 – 40 years, with Diploma/S1 education, occupation employees/students, at least those who visit 4 times to 5 times, while on the 1st visit, the 2nd visit 2 times, 3 times, and more than 5 times is relatively high, gets information from brochures/friends/internet, is willing to come back, thinks the price is right, thinks the location is good, and places the product/service as the most important.

Among the characteristics and products/services of the Spa there is a relationship as follows:

Consumer Characteristics	General Spa Satisfaction
Citizenship	No connection
Gender	There is a relationship Women are more satisfied than men
Age	There is a relationship Young age is more satisfied than old age
Education	No connection
Profession	No connection
Visit to-	There is a relationship The more often you visit the more satisfied
Source of Info	No connection
Willingness	There is a relationship. Those who are willing are more satisfied than those who are not
Price	There is a relationship. Those who agree that the price is good are more satisfied than not
Location	No connection

B. Suggestions

Based on the conclusions above, as well as the information obtained during the research, it is suggested that because consumers place the product/service as the most important thing, the Spa should pay more attention to its handling. Giving more attention to the therapists, which involves improving skills, satisfaction and a supportive work atmosphere, a more motivating incentive system, and others. Improvement of facilities and therapy rooms, so that consumers are more satisfied physically and mentally. It is

suggested to the company to further research why consumers are only interested in traditional treatments. So, companies can take better steps, in terms of training, pricing, or in terms of costs.

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